

LUMINESCENT METHOD OF ASSESSING THE STRUCTURAL MODIFICATIONS OF POLYMER MATRICES

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1 Introduction

Technology, transportation, communication, planning and many other structures that provide the existence and development of the modern society widely use electronics and composite materials. One of the areas of new solutions and materials is molecular electronics in combination with molecular sensors and nano-materials that are based on the use of organic materials. This is due to much larger variety of structural and physico-chemical properties of organic materials in comparison with inorganic. They also have an important ability to continuously change their modifications in order to change their mechanical and physical properties smoothly and in the right direction. Organic substances in the condensed state (polymers and ordered films, liquid and molecular crystals) are characterized by weak intermolecular bonds. In this regard, an organic molecule in the condensed phase retains much of its personality, and the properties of the organic polymer appear as peculiar interlacement of the properties of individual molecules and the collective properties of the polymer.

A number of publications are devoted to study the effect of temperature on the optical characteristics of various compounds (for example, see the reviews in [1–5]). Owing to the wide prospects of applications of optical methods for detecting temperature, interest in the subject matter is still keen. In particular, a number of advanced measurement methods include perspective optical sensors, the principle of which is based on temperature quenching of luminescence.

Luminescent spectroscopy is widely used in research, development and manufacturing of synthetic and natural polymers and composite materials [6–8]. As a technique in polymer chemistry, it is valued for the versatility, high

selectivity and sensitivity of luminescence which originates from the numerous aspects the chemical and physical interactions of molecules excited states with their neighboring environment. Many organic dyes have been found to be excellent microscopic probes when inserted into polymer system and their fluorescence is used to measure and monitor various processes. For example, they are used in monitoring polymerization when a material undergoes a transformation from a viscous liquid to a rigid state when viscosity of the material changes dramatically. Fluorescence of the dyes is still highly sensitive to detect polymeric chain mobility and thermal transitions that affect macromolecular segments. As a result, stresses and degradation of polymeric materials that are caused by exposure to various factors such as heat, ultraviolet light and microbial contamination can also be monitored.

In general, research and development and industry have been using two types of fluorescent probes [7, 8], one is to detect and identify functional groups in materials, and the other is to determine properties of polymers and reactions of polymerization. Over the last three decades, an enormous variety of fluorescent probes has been developed, and one of them is a group of organic compounds known as “molecular rotors” [9, 10]. These compounds exhibit the internal molecular rotation and form so called twisted intramolecular charge transfer states upon light excitation. When excited, the molecular rotor either emits a red-shifted fluorescence or returns to the ground state by non-radiative loss of energy. The internal molecular rotation of a molecular rotor depends on the rigidity of its environment, viscosity and free volume available for mechanical relaxation of the excited molecule. As a result, a yield of the molecular rotor fluorescence is highly sensitive to such parameters as reaction of polymerization, polymer molecular

weight, and stereoregularity of polymer chains, chain crosslinking, relaxation and flexibility. The maximum of a molecular rotor emission also depends on the surrounding media polarity that allows for mapping the probe locations in the polymeric matrix by molecular imaging techniques [11].

Triphenylmethane dyes, the structural formula of which is presented below, do not luminesce in liquid

due to the loss of the electronic excitation of the molecule as a result of the relative movement of benzene rings connected via the flexible chain -C-C-[1] of carbon atoms (where R_1 , R_2 , R_3 – functional groups, and An^- –anion) due to the thermal diffusion. This type of dyes was probably one of the first molecular rotors used to study properties of polymer matrices and materials [12–14]. The quantum yield of the dyes fluorescence was determined as a function of viscosity of the polymeric environment in the power of $2/3$. Triphenylmethane dyes showed a high sensitivity to temperature of the polymeric solutions. In highly viscous solutions, their fluorescence quantum yields ranged from 0.3 to 0.8 decreased significantly with increasing temperature by a factor of 100 and greater [13].

It was found that upon the introduction of triphenylmethane dyes into a solid matrix of poly(methacrylic) acid the dyes molecules begin to luminesce [12–15]. According to our study, described below, luminescence of triphenylmethane dyes also arises in the matrices of other polymers that form true solutions with the dyes, such as polyvinyl alcohol, polymethyl methacrylate and polyvinyl butyral (PVB).

PVB refers to amorphous polymers, the thermodynamic state of which varies in a relatively small range of temperatures. Even at 60°C - 80°C , it goes from the glassy into high elastic state and at temperatures above 100°C - into a viscous fluid. It is known [16] that the properties of amorphous polymers are highly dependent on their history: thermal, mechanical, the dissolution in solvents of

different thermodynamic quality, etc. This is due to the fact that the amorphous state is non-equilibrium, and within it, different structural forms with different properties can be formed. We have suggested that in an environment like the PVB, the temperature will affect the luminescence of triphenylmethane dyes by changing the structure and mobility of the polymer chains and links, as this will lead to a change in the mobility of the rings of the dye molecule and the redistribution of the probability of nonradiative and radiative processes deactivation of the energy of its electronic excitation.

2 Results and Discussion

2.1 Experimental

Experimentally, the spectral characteristics of triphenylmethane dyes such as crystal violet (CV), bromophenol blue (BB), bromophenol red (BR), methyl violet, introduced in the PVB, were studied with a standard spectrophotometer (SPEKOL-220) and custom made highly sensitive spectrofluorometer.

It is known that in liquids triphenylmethane dyes have the ability to easily form associates. In amorphous polymers because of their irregular structure, there are areas with different concentrations of impurity centers. This in turn has influence on the association of the dye molecules and on their spectral characteristics. Fig. 1 shows the absorption and fluorescence spectra of BPhB in the PVB films depending of the dye concentration. As one can see, with increasing concentration of dye molecules, the optical density of the absorption increases, which is accompanied by a deformation of the absorption band. As the concentration of the dye increases, the intensity of the main peak ($\lambda = 580$ nm) of the monomer absorption decreases, then disappears, and there appear short-wave bands at 415 and 320 nm corresponding to dimers and larger associates. The fluorescence intensity first increases with the concentration and then decreases. This is explained by the concentration quenching of the fluorescence. A similar behavior of the spectral characteristics was observed for the dyes BR and CV: with increasing temperature, their luminescence spectra shift to longer wavelengths.

The obtained data indicates that the process of the molecular association of triphenylmethane

dyes takes place in the PVB films. As for the BB dye, the monomers become fully associated and form luminescent associates at least of two types.

In the study of a number of triphenylmethane dyes embedded into a polymer matrix of PVB there was observed temperature dependence of their spectral properties. These are:

- The emergence of thermal hysteresis of the luminescence intensity of the dyes in the range of one cycle (heating polymeric samples from 20° C to 100° C and then cooling them to room temperature.) The value of the fluorescence intensity of the dye at 20° C after one cycle was reduced by 15% (Fig. 2), i.e. there was observed the temperature hysteresis.
- The disappearance of the luminescence of the dyes at 100° C and higher.

It is known that the luminescence intensity of dyes is sensitive to steric factors, that is, the position of the dye molecules with respect to the environment. Due to the fact that in subsequent cycles "heating-cooling" the molecule polymer chain links will not come back to the original position, in each cycle the geometry of the environment of the dye molecules changes. This leads to the fact that at the end of each cycle, the value of the luminescence intensity in this temperature point is different from the previous one (temperature hysteresis is observed).

Given that the thermal quenching of the luminescence is due, above all, to the structural heterogeneity of polymer medium that increases with increasing temperature, in our study, we deliberately changed the structure of the polymer. We have applied various methods of structural modifications of PVB allowing for transferring the polymer kept at room temperature from the glassy into high state which is characterized by thermal stability. Structural modifications of PVB were done by the introduction of various additives, heat treatment and annealing. It can be expected that with irradiation of the impurity centers, the dye molecules residing in such matrices with additives, there will be observed stable values of the luminescence intensity for every fixed temperature during the repeated heating and cooling of the film.

Various types of stabilizers, fillers, surfactants and plasticizers were used as additives. Stabilizers are low molecular weight organic and inorganic compounds that slow the aging process of

polymers occurring in them under the influence of elevated temperatures, different types of radiation, mechanical stress in the presence of oxygen and as well as in vacuum [16–17]. Depending on the functions of the additives, their content in the polymer material may vary from fractions of a percent (stabilizers) to ten and more percent (fillers). The introduction into the polymer matrix of different fillers, with the content reached tens of percents by weight of the polymer, has not led to the disappearance of the temperature hysteresis. With the introduction of different stabilizers in the amount of 0.1, 0.3, 0.5, and 1% of the volume of the polymer containing the dye, visible changes in the observations of the temperature hysteresis have not been revealed. In addition, almost identical results were obtained for different percentages of the additives, fillers and stabilizers. The introduction of stearic acid into the samples as a surfactant resulted in the increase of the hysteresis (the fluorescence intensity of the dye at 20° C after one cycle decreased by 20% ÷ 30%). At the same time, there was observed a simultaneous broadening of the luminescence spectra.

As already mentioned above, the structure of a polymer is also affected by the introduction of a plasticizer. Plasticizers improve ductility of a polymer material, elasticity, and increase its temperature resistance. In this case, with increasing plasticizer content the glass transition temperature naturally decreases. The studies have shown [18,19] that, when the plasticizer dihexyl adipate is added to the samples, the temperature hysteresis observed in non-plasticized samples becomes not greater than 1% – 2% or is not detected at all. It has been also observed that after some time (2–3 days) the hysteresis appears again. This may be due to the migration of the plasticizer to the surface of the polymer because of its relatively large content (38%) that is higher than the equilibrium concentration of the plasticizer limit compatibility with the polymer matrix.

It is known [16–17] that heating can cause an additional structuring of PVB. That is, the formation of a spatial network by bridging the chemical bond between the carbon atoms of adjacent monomer units of the polymer chain is possible without introducing special additives as it is done by oxygen from the air. In this regard, the targeted

changes in the structure of amorphous PVB were also carried out by heat treatment and annealing.

Heat treatment of not plasticized samples was as follows: liquid polymer with the imbedded dye molecules (before spraying it on the substrate) was heated to 40° C ÷ 70° C. The best result of the films prepared in this way was obtained with a sample which has undergone heat treatment at a temperature of 65° C. The thermal hysteresis of the fluorescence dye crystal violet in this case was 2% ÷ 3%. For the remaining samples, the thermal hysteresis was equal to 8% ÷ 10% for the films heat treated at 40° C and 5% ÷ 6% for the films are heat treated at 70° C.

Upon annealing the sample (heating the film without the addition of other substances for 30 minutes to 60° C and cooling naturally for 60 minutes at room temperature), the thermal hysteresis is not observed. However, 10 ÷ 12 hours later after the annealing (that appears to be the bulk relaxation time of the polymer to return to the initial state) the hysteresis of the dye fluorescence reappears.

The results of the study of CV in the plasticized PVB film are shown in Fig. 3.

It is known that molecules of monomers and associates differently interact with the environment [1,2]. Furthermore, the process of association depends on the temperature. It is expected that the degree of change in structure and homogeneity of the polymer medium due to the movement of the polymer chains and links will affect the process of association of the dye molecules. Fig. 4 shows the fluorescence spectrum of BB introduced in the plasticized PVB matrix and heated from 20°C to 50° C at the dye concentration 10⁻² mole/l. It can be seen that with increasing temperature the intensity of the luminescence dye is significantly reduced, while the deformation of the emission spectrum is observed: the spectrum narrows and the difference between the two maxima of the emission becomes less clear. The intensity of fluorescence of the BB associates ($\lambda = 630$ nm) with the temperature decreases much faster than the fluorescence of the monomers ($\lambda = 560$ nm). Thus, it is seen that the temperature has a different effect on the fluorescence intensity of the associates and monomers of triphenylmethane dyes in polymeric matrices.

We have carried out measurements on the effect of temperature on fluorescence spectral

characteristics of the dyes monomers, dimers and larger associates embedded in the plasticized polymer samples. The results of the measurements are shown in Table 1 (the measurement temperature was varied from 20° C to 60° C). Thermal sensitivity k was determined by the formula:

$$k = \frac{I_1 - I_2}{I_1 \Delta t} \cdot 100\% ,$$

where I_1, I_2 – the fluorescence intensity at 20° C and 60° C, respectively, Δt – the absolute value of the temperature range.

As seen from the table, the associates have greater temperature sensitivity in comparison with the monomers. The associates' higher temperature sensitivity can be explained by the fact that, in addition to the influence of temperature on the mobility of the rings of the dye molecules, temperature also affects the formation and decay of the associates.

Thus, the obtained experimental results support the fact that the effect of temperature on the luminescence of triphenylmethane dyes embedded in a polymer matrix of PVB is owing to changes in the internal structure of the environment surrounding the dye molecule. Triphenylmethane dyes, because of the flexible connection between the benzene rings, track changes in the environment due to the influence of the latter on the mobility of the molecular skeleton. In other words, the molecules of these dyes are a kind of structure sensor of the environment, which opens up new prospects for their use, for example, to study phase transitions in polymers.

2.2 Quantum-chemical modeling

Thus, it has been shown that the luminescence of organic molecules CV depends on the state of their environment. This allows for obtaining information about the structural transformations of the environment owing to the changes of the intensity of the CV luminescence and its spectrum.

When temperature changes, polymer chains partially change their position relative to the dye molecules embedded in a polymer matrix, and this, in our opinion, causes the appearance of the hysteresis. Therefore, by setting various locations of the CV dye molecule relatively to PVB chains, it is possible to calculate the CV fluorescence spectrum under those conditions and compare the intensities of the wavelengths allowed transitions. Based on this assumption, we carried out a computer simulation of the matrices under a condition that structuring of the matrices is caused by oxygen from the air in the films prepared by annealing or heat treatment of the liquid polymer.

The size of the PVB chain containing 6 monomers of the following type

is much larger than the size of one CV molecule. Therefore, the spectroscopic effect, calculated theoretically and related to the change in the luminescence intensity of the dye should be manifested at different positions of a CV molecule relatively to even a single polymer chain.

Fig. 5 shows a different arrangement of the dye molecules with respect to a single chain modeling the polymer. The distance from the dye molecule to the PVB polymer chain is 3 Å – 4 Å, but not greater than 5 Å.

The effectiveness of the methods of computational chemistry, among which are the methods of molecular mechanics and semi-empirical quantum chemistry, is now sufficiently high. The existing software packages such as MOPAC, AMPAC and HYPERCHEM allow for a comprehensive analysis and interpretation of numerous experimental data on the basis of quantum-chemical structure of the dye. Quantum-chemical calculations appear to be the only source of undeveloped information about the structure of and energy transition states, which in principle cannot be observed experimentally, as well as highly labile intermediates that are very difficult to observe due to the extremely high rate of conversion.

The calculation of the wavelengths of spectral lines in the CV geometry optimization of

the dye-polymer was carried out by the method of molecular mechanics Mm+, along with the semi-empirical method ZINDO1. These methods are implemented in a software package. The choice of these methods is due to both the objects and tasks in research. For this purpose one can use only computational methods that can examine molecules with conjugated bonds, considering the interaction of many tens of atoms, and allow for taking into account the specific types of hydrogen bond interactions or a donor-acceptor interaction and interaction of chromophoric cation conjugates.

Method MM + accounts the potential fields generated by all atoms of the calculated system and allows for flexibly modifying the parameters of the calculation depending on the particular task making it, on the one hand, the most common and, on the other hand, it greatly increases the necessary resources in comparison with other methods of molecular mechanics.

Semi-empirical methods solve the Schrödinger equation for atoms and molecules with the use of certain approximations and simplifications. All the methods of this group are characterized by the following: the calculation is only for the valence electrons, the values of the integrals of certain interactions are neglected, they use the standard non-optimized basis functions of the electronic orbitals and some of the parameters obtained in the experiment. Semi-empirical methods are easier to use than all the empirical ones and, with a suitable choice of the parameters, they are in better agreement with experiment as the empirical values of the integrals implicitly take into account the distortion of the atomic orbitals in a molecule and partly absorb the errors introduced by the approximation. The method ZINDO/1 is a variant of the method INDO (Intermediate Neglect of Differential Overlap) adapted for the calculation of molecules including atoms of the transition elements. It is used to calculate the ground-state electronic properties of systems with open and closed electron shell, optimization of the geometry and the total energy, and it is different from the original method by using permanent orbital exponents.

The calculation shows one line which lies in the range of 400 nm – 600 nm which can be correlated and compared with the experimental spectrum. Even the results of these simple

calculations let confirm the mechanism of the appearance of the hysteresis as a change in the geometry of the dye environment. Indeed, for the second and third modifications (Fig. 3b, c), the intensities of the calculated spectral lines of the 0–0 transition ($\lambda = 569$ nm) are different.

A detailed absorption spectrum of the CV molecule as a set of frequencies of the transition $S_0 - S_1$ to various vibrational levels of the excited state S_1 has never been calculated. As a result, it is unknown which vibrational level of the S_1 state is associated with the maximum of the absorption band. However, the calculation shows only one line which can be correlated and compared with the experimental spectrum.

Apparently, the simulation of the polymer in the form of several PVB chains does not change this qualitative mechanism of the hysteresis.

As annealing of the polymeric films should lead to stable structural modifications of the polymer chains with respect to the dye molecules, the hysteresis should disappear (a polymer molecule does not change its position relatively to the dye molecule when the temperature of the films changes from 20° C to 90° C), as it is observed in the experiment.

Quantum-chemical modeling by means of the molecular mechanics and semi-empirical method ZINDO1 allowed for proposing geometric models of the dye molecule with respect to the location of a single chain of the polymer that are most relevant to the experimental spectral data. The mathematical calculations yielded the results that are in qualitative agreement with the experimental data. The data relates to the changes of the fluorescence intensity of the dye in the polymer matrix under various structural modifications. In addition, the calculations let evaluate the mechanisms of degradation of the polymer.

3 Conclusions

Results of our study of the effects of temperature and changes in the structure of the polymer matrix on the fluorescence emission of the impurity centers have shown that

- the appearance of the luminescence of triphenylmethane dyes, depending on

temperature, when administered in a polymeric matrix;

- the disappearance of their luminescence at temperatures above 100° C;
- the thermal hysteresis phenomenon of the luminescence of the dyes centers in polymer matrices;
- the disappearance of the hysteresis of the luminescence as a result of the changes in the state (properties) of the polymer by plasticizing;
- the different sensitivity of the monomers and associates to temperature change

are explained by the change in the internal structure of the environment surrounding the dye molecule. The results of calculations with the methods MM+ and ZINDO/1 confirm the mechanism of the thermal hysteresis as a change in the geometry of the environment of the luminescence centers. The calculated electrons spectra clarify the geometry of the structure of the dye molecule. The data obtained reveals perspectives for the use of triphenylmethane dyes as sensors that analyze the physical state of polymers and allows for comparing their structural features.

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Fig. 1. The absorption spectra of (1-3) and fluorescence (1'-3') of bromophenol blue in the unplasticized PVB films at various concentrations at 20° C. Spectral lines 1 and 1', 2 and 2', 3 and 3' correspond to the concentrations of the bromophenol blue centers 10^{-4} mole/l, 10^{-3} mole/l and 10^{-2} mole/l, respectively.

Fig. 2. The dependence of the normalized intensity of the fluorescence of the dye bromophenol blue at the wavelength of the maximum radiation in the film of polyvinyl butyral on the temperature of the film during one cycle of «20° C → 50° C → 20° C»

Fig. 3. Absorption (1) and luminescence (2–5) of the dye crystal violet (the concentration of the dye molecules $C = 10^{-2}$ mole/l) in plasticized polyvinyl butyral film. Spectral lines 2, 3, 4 and 5 correspond to the film temperature 20° C, 40° C, 60° C and 70° C. The film thickness is ≈ 8 microns.

Fig. 4. The spectra of bromophenol blue ($C = 10^{-2}$ mole/l) in the plasticized PVB film depending on temperature: 1 - 20° C, 2 - 30° C, 3 - 35° C, 4 - 40° C, 5 - 45° C and 6 - 50° C. The film thickness is ≈ 8 microns.

Fig. 5a

Fig. 5b

Fig. 5c

Fig. 5a - 5c. Various modifications of the molecules of the dye crystal violet relatively to the chain of the polymer

Table 1. Temperature sensitivity of the monomers and associates of triphenylmethane dyes (λ is wavelength of the fluorescence maximum intensity)

Dye	Temperature sensitivity k , [% / C]	
Bromo-phenol Blue		2.40 ($\lambda = 630$ nm)
Bromo-phenol Red	1.2 ($\lambda = 560$ nm)	1.73 ($\lambda = 580$ nm)
Crystal Violet	0.99 ($\lambda = 630$ nm)	1.28 ($\lambda = 690$ nm)